

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

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Unusual fish killing blooms of *Triplos furca* in Van Phong Bay, South Viet Nam

Fig. 1. a) Map of Vietnam and the study area (framed with a square). b) High resolution satellite images during this period were rare due to cloudy weather conditions. An image from 9th November shows patches of the bloom spreading over the inner part of Van Phong Bay. (Source: ESA, Sensinel-2 colour composite, processed by Tong Phuoc Hoang Son, Institute of Oceanography, Viet Nam).

In the beginning of November 2016, a phytoplankton bloom was observed by fisherman in Van Phong Bay, Viet Nam with red-brown patches spreading over the inner part of the bay. Although no fish mortality was reported at the time, the patches raised concern among fish farmers in the area, and samples were sent to the Institute of Oceanography. The bloom forming species was identified as *Triplos furca*. This bloom developed throughout November and mass mortality of wild and caged fish occurred during the last part of the month.

Bloom development

The earliest sign of a developing bloom was retrieved from satellite images on 14th October 2016 in the inner part of Van Phong Bay (Fig. 1). A sample on 30th October confirmed a high density of *T. furca*. From late October to early November heavy rainfall occurred in the Khanh Hoa Province, with a maximum of 400 mm per day. After the 6th November, rainfall was very weak or even absent in the Province (data from Provincial meteorological station, not shown). Nutrient data are not available but runoff following the heavy rainfall may have favoured the development of the bloom.

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Fig. 2. Chl-a distribution in coastal waters of Khanh Hoa province during 14th October to 25th November 2016 (sources: MODIS-Aqua Level 2 images, NASA). Clear skies were observed on 14th October, and 11th, 13th, 15th, 22nd, 25th November, while the other days were very cloudy. High chl-a concentrations were seen on 11th and 13th November in the northern part of Van Phong Bay and on 22nd November, chl-a patches.

The dominant species in all plankton samples was *T. furca* with *Peridinium quinquecorne* (up to $1.3 \cdot 10^6$ cells·L⁻¹ on 26th November) also blooming in a small area in the southwestern part of the bay. During the bloom of *T. furca*, the species diversity was low (2-38 species recorded in the samples). During the period from 28th November to the 1st December, cell densities reached $3.9 \cdot 10^6$ cells·L⁻¹ (Fig. 4). At the same time, cell density of *T. furca* outside Van Phong Bay, near Dai Lanh Beach, was only 280 cells·L⁻¹.

Fish mortality was first observed in early November when ca. 35 t of caged fish were killed. This incident affected 260 households in Dam Mon and was attributed to the extremely heavy rainfall which may have reduced the salinity of the surface water within a very short period of time [1].

Harmful effects

During the second and third week of November the fishermen observed increasing discolouration of the water and occasional death of young and non-healthy lobsters and 3-5 kg size cobia fish (*Rachycentron canadum*) (Fig. 3b). On November 24th, mortality of marine animals mounted to an estimated 15 t and included wild fish as well as farmed fish (about 7 t of cobia, 1000 young lobsters and 500 kg of cultured snails [2] (Fig. 3a). A few days later, on 29 November in Dam Mon, an estimated 200 t of caged cobia died and the economic loss amounted to about ca. 1 million US dollars.

The dinoflagellate *T. furca* is not known to be a toxin producing species but it may form high-biomass blooms causing damage through secondary effects such as oxygen depletion. In North

Viet Nam it formed a high-biomass bloom in Ha Long Bay in July 2011 killing 10 t of caged groupers and snappers [3]. There are several previous reports of blooms of *T. furca* associated with mortality of fish or other marine fauna including Hong Kong [4], Japan [5], South Africa [6], and Mexico [7]. Low oxygen concentrations may be part of the reason for the observed mortality but clogging and physical damage to fish gills leading severe mucus production almost certainly also plays a role [7].

Data on oxygen levels from the bloom area in Van Phong Bay are not available. However, there was strong indications of gill damage in dead 3-10 kg fish collected on 28th November. Dissection of fish at the Institute of Oceanography in Nha Trang showed congestion of gill arches and gill filaments and large amounts of mucus.

There is no regular government-based HAB monitoring in Van Phong Bay. During the development of the bloom information and warnings were sent directly to the fish farmers from the scientists at ION through personal contacts. According to the fish farmers, the information provided helped mitigate the harmful effects as planned new stocks for the aquacultures were postponed, feeding was reduced, and fish and lobster pens were moved to safer areas. Blooms of *Noctiluca scintillans* [8], and *T. trichoceros* [9], have been reported previously in the bay. Considering the recent expansion of aquaculture activities and the planned industrial and tourist development, there is an urgent need for regular HAB monitoring in Van Phong Bay.

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Fig. 3. a) Brown colour water inside the fish cages (Photo provided by a local fish culture company) and b) Fish mortality at the pier (Photo by Hai Lang - Van Giang, Khanhhoa-Online, issue date: November 25th).

Fig. 4. Variation of cell density (cells/L) of *T. furca* during November 26th to December 1st 2016 at different sampling stations.

Mortality of Chilean farmed salmon in wellboats in transit through a *Karenia* bloom

Fig. 1. Geographic distribution of the stations sampled near the Gulf of Penas, Chile, between 31st January and 1st February 2017.

A mass mortality of around 170,000 salmon, worth US\$ 390,000, was recorded on wellboats in transit between the Magallanes and Los Lagos regions (Southern Chile) on January 26th, 2017. Investigations into the environmental causes were pursued after technical and operational failures (e.g. oxygen depletion) were ruled out. From the onset, harmful algal blooms (HAB) were suspected as the most probable cause as the area is known for previous large-scale blooms including non-toxic diatoms belonging to the genera *Chaetoceros* and *Rhizosolenia*, toxic phytoplankton, such as *Heterosigma akashiwo* and *Pseudochattonella verruculosa*, and toxic dinoflagellates (*Alexandrium* and *Karenia*). Blooms of different geographical scales, including some significant events, have been recorded in the affected area [1, 2]. The occurrence of toxin producing HABs has been related to anomalous sea surface temperature (SST) and weather conditions such as

those associated with El Niño [2].

Environmental variables, including SST, salinity and pH were measured in 10 sampling stations between the Gulf of Penas and Moraleda Channel (Fig. 1) between January 31st and February 2nd, 2017. Synoptic overviews of SST, chlorophyll-a concentration and oxygen saturation distributions were obtained

from the analysis of MODIS/AQUA satellite images. Surface water samples were fixed with acidic Lugol's solution and analyzed according to the Utermöhl technique for identification and enumeration of phytoplankton.

Satellite images of the Gulf of Penas, Taitao Peninsula and Pulluche Channel showed the presence of sub-Antarctic water masses (ASAA) characterized by salinity values of 34-36, and temperatures between 11.5 and 13.6 °C (Fig. 2), whereas the southern part of the Gulf of Penas (station 13) and the stations at Moraleda Channel showed modified sub-Antarctic water masses (ASAAM), which were colder and with lower (29-30) salinities due to runoff from glaciers and rivers [3]. The seawater pH varied between values close to 7 in the Gulf of Penas to around 8 in the remaining stations (Fig. 2). Satellite-derived chlorophyll-a concentrations were close to 5 µg L⁻¹, and oxygen saturation was 44.4%. The lower pH and oxygen in waters from the Gulf of Penas may have been related to coastal upwelling in the area.

Phytoplankton in the water samples was diverse, with diatoms and dinoflagellates being the most abundant taxonomic groups. A marked difference was observed between stations 13 to 20 (Gulf of Penas and Taitao Peninsula) and stations 21 to 23 (Pulluche and Moraleda Channels). The first group of stations presented a phytoplankton community typical of oceanic waters, with dominance of unarmoured dinoflagellates of the genus *Karenia* which represented 21 to 91% of the total abundance. The second group of stations (21 to 23) showed a phytoplankton community, characteristic of the fjords and chan-

Fig. 2. Sea Surface temperature (°C), pH and salinity (PSU) across the sampled stations in the vicinity of the Gulf of Penas.

Fig. 3. Density (cells L⁻¹) of *Karenia* spp. in water samples of the vicinity of the Gulf of Penas.

nels, composed mainly of diatoms.

Most *Karenia* (ex *Gymnodinium*) species produce toxins that can kill fish and other marine organisms when they bloom. In addition to toxicity, some *Karenia* blooms cause animal mortalities through the generation of anoxia and at least one species, *K. brevis*, produces brevetoxins that not only kills fish, marine mammals, and other animals, but also causes neurotoxic shellfish poisoning (NSP) and respiratory distress in humans exposed to the toxic sea spray associated with the blooms [4,5].

Samples showed a high density of *Karenia* species (up to 65 x 10³ cells L⁻¹; average of 19.4 x 10³ cells L⁻¹) representing between 0 and 91% of the total phytoplankton community. Densities of *Karenia* spp. in the Gulf of Penas varied

between 2 x 10³ cells L⁻¹ (station 13) and 65 x 10³ cells L⁻¹ (station 14), while stations around the Taitao Peninsula (18, 19, 20) showed densities of 31, 19 and 17 x 10³ cells L⁻¹ respectively (Fig. 3). The distribution of *Karenia* spp. was restricted to areas with a high influence of oceanic waters, and was not recorded in Pulluche and Moraleda Canal (stations 21 and 22). The bloom of *Karenia* was multispecific, including a variety of forms resembling *Karenia brevis*, *K. papilionacea*, *K. mikimotoi*, *K. brevisulcata* and *K. bidigitata*. (Fig 4). The dominant *Karenia* form was *Karenia* sp 1 (Fig. 4c) and had an approximate width of 28.8 μm and length of 32 μm.

The phytoplankton communities and environmental variables varied in the study area from typically oceanic, with upwelled waters with lower-pH

Fig. 4. Light microscope images (400X) of different species of *Karenia* present in the vicinity of the Gulf of Penas. A) *Karenia* cf *mikimotoi*; B) *K. cf digitata*; C) *Karenia* sp1; D) *Karenia* sp 2; E) *K. cf papilionacea*/*K. cf brevis*. Size bar = 30 μm.

and oxygen levels (Gulf of Penas and Taitao Peninsula), to those characteristic from more brackish waters from fjords and channels (Moraleda Channel). The oceanic phytoplankton was dominated by ichthyotoxic dinoflagellates of the genus *Karenia*, which were identified as the most probable cause of the mortality of the salmon in wellboats during their passage through the Gulf of Penas. The high toxicity of *Karenia* spp. was evidenced by the rapid death of salmon on board.

Multispecific blooms of the genus *Karenia* have been described before [6]. Here we describe a multispecific bloom with the co-occurrence of at least 5 species of *Karenia*. The presence of multiple ichthyotoxic species of *Karenia* and the difficulty to observe features of naked dinoflagellates after fixation made identification to species level unattainable. There are studies in progress to describe the specimens after further examinations by scanning electron microscopy, and molecular studies.

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A bloom of *Amphidinium carterae* in Ria de Aveiro, Portugal

Fig. 1. Ria de Aveiro and oyster farm location.

Amphidinium carterae is a benthic unarmored cosmopolitan dinoflagellate classed as a fish killer due to its capacity to produce hemolytic compounds such as amphidinols [1] and polyhydroxyl carteranol E [2]. This species can be found in shallow and sheltered waters in intertidal or estuarine marine sandy sediments, from tropical, subtropical and temperate ecosystems [3,4].

Between March 24th to March 29th 2016, a bloom of *Amphidinium carterae* was detected in an oyster farm (area of 6 ha, water column of 30-60 cm depth with oyster production of 2kg m⁻²) in Ria de Aveiro (Fig 1). Dinoflagellate cell densities reached 5.4 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹ and oysters suffered significant weight loss.

Ria de Aveiro is the largest Portuguese tidal coastal lagoon, extending 45km N-S and about 10 km E-W, between the Aveiro city and the Atlantic Ocean. It has a single connection with the sea and has inputs from two main rivers and several smaller streams [5]. This aquatic system had ancient salt flats that were converted to fish and shellfish farms with tidally regulated water inflow. In this coastal lagoon, aquaculture has a great social and economic importance [6]. The *Amphidinium* bloom was recorded within the shellfish pond and decreased towards the main branch of the Ria. Within the pond, the water presented a brown-reddish color, was cold (12.4-12.9 °C), brackish (20.9-28) and slightly basic (pH of 8.0-8.4). The most abundant accompanying species were

Cylindrotheca closterium (7.6 x10⁵ cells L⁻¹), *Amphyprora* sp. (5.4 x10⁵ cells L⁻¹) and *Prorocentrum minimum* (9.8 x 10³ cells L⁻¹). On the day before the sudden increase of cells in the water, the total radiation increased significantly, from 3505 to 19560 KJ m⁻². Values remained that high until the maximum of *Amphi-*

Fig. 2. (A) *Amphidinium carterae* cell (image taken with an LM Leica DMI 8 with 400x magnification). (B) Sample from *Amphidinium carterae* bloom (image taken with an LM Leica DMI 8 with 200x magnification).

dinium developed and these high light levels may have triggered the bloom [7]

Amphidinium carterae was morphologically identified by inverted microscopy (Leica DMI 8) at 400/200x magnification, in natural and in Lugol's preserved samples (Fig. 2A, B). Cell dimensions (n=21) averaged 17µm in length (15.0-20.0 µm) and 10.4 µm in width (10.0-12.5 µm), within the range defined for the species [8]. *Amphidinium* was isolated and cultured for molecular identification based on the Large Ribosomal Subunit (28S) with the primers pair D1R/D3Ca [9]. In a Blast search, our sequences showed 99% similarity with 100% cover and E-value of zero compared to the Genbank sequence JQ394805.1.

Although the presence of the species is expected to be among those listed in the National HAB monitoring plan, the last reported occurrence of *A. carterae* in Portuguese estuarine waters dates back to 1985 [10]. This event reinforces the need to monitor the species occurrence and the associated environmental conditions in estuarine systems to forecast blooms and minimize social-economic impacts.

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Harmful dinoflagellates in the Gulf of Guinea, Nigeria, West Africa

Fig. 1. Coastal map of Nigeria showing the study area.

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) are worldwide phenomena [1]. The increasing spread, frequency and severity of harmful algal incidents have been well documented and have led to the establishment of harmful algal monitoring programs in coastal states in developed countries around the world. This is not the case in several West African countries, including Nigeria, for a variety of reasons. These include a lack of awareness of HABs and the threats they pose, funding difficulties and others. Several coastal communities in Nigeria depend heavily on seafood for their nutritional and economic subsistence and as such will be directly affected by the health, economic and ecosystem disruption impacts caused by HABs.

This report is based on quarterly HAB surveys of the Nigerian coast situated in the Guinea Current Large Marine Ecosystem, in the Gulf of Guinea which span eight coastal states in the south (Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross Rivers, Delta and Rivers states) and south west (Badagry, Bar Beach, Lekki, Ogun and Ondo states) of Nigeria (Fig. 1). The country coastline, between latitude 4°10'– 6°20' N and longitude 2°45'– 8°35' E, is approximately 853 km long. It is composed of four distinct geomorphological units, namely: the Barrier-Lagoon complex; the Mud coast; the Arcuate Niger Delta; and the

Strand coast [2]. This study marks the first extensive study on HABs in the entire coast of Nigeria. Prior studies [3,4] were based on small spatio-temporal scale data collection.

Sampling was carried out from March 2014 to January 2015; samples were collected with a 10- μ m mesh size net and a known volume of water sedimented for qualitative and quantitative

analyses respectively. Harmful dinoflagellates were quantified following the drop count method described by Lackey [5]. Net samples were analysed using an OLYMPUS optical binocular microscope (CX40RF200) fitted with an AMSCOPE digital imager (Model no: MU1403).

Two hundred and twelve phytoplankton samples from 54 locations collected during each quarterly sampling, were analysed for quantitative and qualitative assessment. From these, a total of 74 dinoflagellates taxa were documented. Cell concentrations were found to be generally higher in the southwest locations (Fig. 2a), with total cell concentrations ranging between 13 and 811 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$ compared to the south locations (Fig. 2b) where total cell concentrations ranged between 13 and 351 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$. We found that the major contributors to the total cell counts in the south were high densities of species of the genera *Alexandrium* (352 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$), *Prorocentrum* (195 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$), *Protoperidinium* (159 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$) and *Tripos* (=Ceratum) (117 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$) in July. In the southwest locations, the major contributors varied depending on the sampling season. For instance *Prorocentrum* spp. (754 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$), *Scrippsiella* sp. (702 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$), *Tripos* spp. (455 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$) and *Protoperidinium* spp. (312 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$) were most abundant in March; *Alexandrium* spp. (546 $\times 10^3 L^{-1}$) and

Fig. 2a-b. Total density of harmful dinoflagellates in the south-west and southern coastal locations of Nigeria.

Plate 1. Light micrographs of some dinoflagellates from Nigerian coastal waters. A. *Prorocentrum* sp.; B. *Prorocentrum micans*; C. *Phalacrocoma hastatum*; D. *Lingulodinium polyedrum*; E. *Protoperidinium elegans*; F. *Tripos* (=Ceratium) *macroceras*; G. *Tripos* cf *vulture*; H. *Dinophysis caudata*; I. *Gymnodinium catenatum*; J. *Noctiluca scintillans*; K. *Alexandrium* sp.; L. *Prorocentrum gracile*; M. *Tripos furca*.

Tripos ($354 \times 10^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$) in October while *Prorocentrum* spp. and *Scrippsiella* spp. showed cell maxima of $871 \times 10^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ and $549 \times 10^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ respectively in January.

Qualitative data showed *Alexandrium* spp., *Tripos furca*, *Tripos fusus*, *Prorocentrum micans*, *P. gracile*, *Lingulodinium polyedrum*, *Heterocapsa niei* and *Scrippsiella trochoidea* as the most widely distributed taxa in the study area (Plate 1).

Increased occurrence of harmful algae in recent years have been ascribed to coastal eutrophication, global climate change as well as increased awareness [6]. Higher cell numbers of harmful dinoflagellates in the south-west locations relative to the other locations may be due to increased nutrient inputs via effluent discharge from various in-

dustries found especially in Lagos and Ogun States and several coastal development projects particularly in Lagos. On the other hand, low cell densities of harmful dinoflagellates observed in the south are attributable to lower salinities owing to the diluting effect of the Niger deltaic inflow into the Gulf of Guinea [7]

A number of harmful effects [8] have been ascribed to the dinoflagellates found in our studies, including species that can form high biomass blooms and cause indiscriminate kills of fish and invertebrates through oxygen depletion, clogging and excess mucus stimulation of fish gills. Included among these are *Tripos furca*, *T. fusus*, *T. tripos*, *Prorocentrum micans*, *Noctiluca scintillans* and *Scrippsiella trochoidea*. Also nota-

ble are toxic harmful dinoflagellates that produce a suite of toxins, including *Alexandrium catenella* and *Gymnodinium catenatum* (saxitoxins), *Dinophysis caudata* (okadaic acid congeners), and benthic HAB (*Ostreopsis* cf *ovata*, palytoxins, and *Prorocentrum lima*, okadaic acid). These toxins can directly impact humans when consumed via contaminated seafood.

This study has shown that harmful dinoflagellates are present in Nigerian waters in high cell densities characteristic of bloom levels. There is the need to undertake a continuous surveillance programme for harmful algal bloom detection. Implementation of routine harmful algal monitoring programmes for Nigeria will provide valuable information for the management of coastal resources and help provide early warning signals of harmful algal bloom events in the region.

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Satellite detection of *Trichodesmium* blooms in the Southwestern Pacific

In the oceans, a large portion of the subtropical and tropical pelagic areas are dominated by oligotrophic conditions. The cyanobacterial diazotroph community, composed of unicellular, filamentous, and diatoms-symbiotic (DDAs, diatom-diazotroph associations) forms is dominant. Major species are *Trichodesmium erythraeum* Ehrenberg and *T. thiebautii* Gomont, two species of *Katagnymene* (*K. pelagica* and *K. spiralis* Lemmerman), and *Richelia intracellularis* as components of DDAs [1]. Weak winds (< 4 m s⁻¹) and calm conditions are independent factors which allow accumulations of *Trichodesmium* on the surface of the sea, in particular *T. erythraeum*, which has a stronger positive buoyancy than *T. thiebautii* and *T. con-*

tortum [1]. Observations of *Trichodesmium* accumulations (termed ‘mats’) around New Caledonia by merchant ships, French Navy, R/V *Alis* and voluntary observers are the result of positive cell buoyancy which brings together trichomes and colonies at the sea surface every summer [2]. *Trichodesmium* is mainly observed around New Caledonia and Vanuatu and a *Katagnymene* form was observed between Niue Island and Tonga in December 2002 [2].

In the southwest tropical Pacific, satellite and aerial observations showed the presence of 3000 km long surface blooms of *Trichodesmium*, mainly around islands of the Melanesian archipelago, i.e. Vanuatu, New Caledonia, and as far east as the Fijian archipelago

and the Tonga trench [2]. This area coincides with high nitrogen fixation rates [3]. There are numerous correlations between the observations of surface mats in the ocean and high reflectance on the MODIS satellite, as for example at the East of New Caledonia in 2002 (Fig. 1a) and 2004 (Fig. 1b, Fig. 1c, Fig. 1d) and in January 2017 (Fig. 1e). In summer 2003, at the peak of a moderate 2001-2003 El Niño, a *Trichodesmium* spp maximum of 4,500 trichomes L⁻¹ was observed in the Loyalty Channel, a concentration much lower than in New Caledonia lagoon surface accumulations which can reach 20,000 trichomes L⁻¹ [4]. *Trichodesmium* blooms may spread to cover enormous sea surface areas. In December 2014, a huge surface bloom detected by MODIS coincided with observations of *Trichodesmium* mats (Fig. 2a,b) during a SPOT cruise on board R/V *Alis* [5] and was followed until March [6]. Mat observations are

Fig. 1a-c) “True color” MODIS images off New Caledonia showing mats as high reflectance in white around the islands. White crosses: Visual observations corresponding to microscope micrographs of *Trichodesmium* in formalin fixed samples collected by the French Navy in: November 2002 (a); January 2004 (b); February 2004 (c). d-f): A mixture of different forms of *Trichodesmium* observed: *T. erythraeum*, *T. thiebautii*, and *Katagnymene spiralis* found in observations on satellite images indicated by a cross. g) Surface *Trichodesmium* mats (from the French Navy ship *La Glorieuse* in January 2004). h) Picture of a mat captured during a New Caledonia *Gardian* aircraft in January 2017 (courtesy Jérôme Aucan).

Fig. 2a) MODIS image of the *Trichodesmium* bloom with white and green mats between Vanuatu Islands and New Caledonia in December 2014; with Landsat 8 zooms on mats superimposed and the microscopic observation of *Trichodesmium* colonies in surface samples at the SPOT station visited with R/V Alis; b) Pictures of *Trichodesmium* mats as photographed from R/V Alis. <http://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/IOTD/view.php?id=85073>

essential for calibrating ocean colour algorithms aimed at detecting filamentous diazotrophs from their particular optical properties. Some of those are pigments (mainly phycoerythrins) absorption and particles backscattering [7] or their ability to float at the surface and present a characteristic optical signature [8]. Application of an algorithm for the satellite detection of *Trichodesmium* mats in oceanic waters of the South Western Tropical Pacific is in progress at the Centre IRD of Noumea [9]. Other phytoplankton blooms around islands in the Tropical Pacific can be detected by MODIS and recent satellite Sentinel sensors. Microscopic identifications of the species involved should be more systematic and observation data centralized.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the French Navy and the Aeronaval Base of New Caledonia for their active participation in the observation programme as well as to the captains and crews of the IRD R/V Alis. We thank Norman Kuring for the NASA MODIS and Landsat 8 images at the NASA web site. We thank Isabelle Biegala for the SPOT (South Pacific Time Series) programme.

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Plankton Planet in New Zealand

Plankton Planet is the first citizen science programme designed for biological oceanography. It is a co-operation between scientists and volunteers from the sailing community based on mass sequencing of DNA barcodes from the extracts of plankton communities collected worldwide. The results of the analysis of samples collected during the 2015 pilot project demonstrated that the quality of the samples was equivalent to that of those obtained during the *Tara* Oceans scientific expeditions. More than 200 million DNA barcodes from 300 samples were generated in the pilot phase. The programme's ability to reach out to sailing communities and recruit citizen "Planktonauts," equip vessels, and coordinate open-ocean sampling of plankton communities across the world oceans has proven it can provide information about plankton communities over spatio-temporal scales never before possible.

The programme is now preparing its next steps for an expansion in geography and duration. To these ends, a week-long scientific workshop is being held in Auckland, New Zealand, in July thanks to a Seeding Fund grant from the New Zealand Ministry of Business,

Innovation & Employment awarded and administered by the Royal Society of New Zealand. It brings together scientists from New Zealand, Europe, and the United States to share recent developments and discuss innovations in collaborative plankton research. Of particular importance is the incorporation of plankton biodiversity (DNA meta-barcoding) data into global oceans models. The scientists will also use this opportunity for outreach to school groups and the general public.

Thanks to the generous support of the New Zealand Maritime Museum and the Sir Peter Blake Trust, an evening programme will be hosted by the Maritime Museum for the general public on 6 July, 2017, at 6:30 p.m. "An Epic Voyage through Our Changing Seas" will bring together New Zealand experts in Māori waka and sailing tradition with international scientists including Prof. Mick Follows, Dr. David Gruber, Dr. Emmanuel Boss, and Dr. Manu Prakash for a series of presentations and discussion with the audience.

From 6 to 30 July, 2017, "Plankton Arts" a display of never-before-seen images of plankton will be on exhibit at the Maritime Museum. Giant prints of

plankton, 3-D models, lenticular prints, and videos aim to bring the microscopic world closer to the public and increase their appreciation of the role plankton plays as basis of the ocean's entire food chain and a regulator of the planet's climate.

For more information see www.planktonplanet.org.

To register for "An Epic Voyage through Our Changing Seas" at the Maritime Museum Auckland, 6 July, 2017, at 6:30 p.m. go to www.EVENTBRITE

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Fig. 1. Marine Plankton. Courtesy of Christian Sardet

Molluscan Shellfish Safety Conference in Ireland

Over 230 international delegates from 27 countries participated in the 11th International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS) from Sunday 14 to Thursday 18 May 2017 at the National University of Ireland, Galway. Convened by Ireland's Marine Institute, the ICMSS is the only international conference that focuses specifically on molluscan shellfish safety, and has previously been hosted by countries including New Zealand, Canada, France, Spain, Australia, USA, and Chile. The 2017 conference programme addressed the themes of protecting consumers, assuring supply and growing confidence. Participants including sea-food safety professionals, scientists, regulators and industry experts discussed these topics and focused on success and innovation in seafood safety and the latest research that will lead us into the future.

Conference Convenor Joe Silke of the Marine Institute said, "The conference was a huge success and was very timely with recent developments in areas of HABs including the occurrence of Tetrodotoxin in European bivalves, blooms of *Alexandrium pseudogonyaulax* and its goniodomines in the Limfjorden (Kattegat) and innovative risk management

and science based models from around the world." The conference hosted sessions on emerging toxin methods and new technology where advances in novel instrumentation and testing methods were presented. Mr Silke said "Ireland has a distinguished track record in the area of molluscan shellfish safety, in developing state-of-the-art monitoring protocols, forecasting tools and a variety of cutting-edge research activities. The ICMSS will help to further increase our knowledge and showcase our commitment to shellfish safety."

The keynote speaker for ICMSS was public health specialist Dorothy-Jean McCoubrey, who has more than 30 years of experience in regulatory roles in New Zealand. Ms McCoubrey said the conference gathers together the world's best experts to achieve two important goals; "The first goal is to dream big with our visionary food safety research. The second is to translate this imaginative foresight into practical and useful material that has the potential to benefit all of society".

Over 70 oral and 46 poster presentations were delivered in 16 themed sessions. The conference keynote presentations were streamed live and over

800 viewers tuned in to these presentations from all over the world. These keynotes were presented by Jim Oliver Bonnie Cone, Distinguished Professor and Professor of Microbiology at the University of North Carolina Charlotte (USA), and Andrew Turner, Principle Chemist at Cefas Weymouth Food Safety Group (UK). There were also keynote presentations from Donald Anderson from Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute (USA), Jan Vinjé from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (USA), Ana Gago-Martinez from the EU Reference Laboratory for Marine Biotoxins (Spain) and Philipp Hess from IFREMER, Nantes (France)

In addition, the ICMSS included a series of five 2 hour workshops on the last day to explore new technologies and regulatory matters in food safety. For more specific information on the content and abstracts at the 2017 conference see www.icmss2017.com

The international conference was hosted by the Marine Institute in association with Bord Iascaigh Mhara, The Food Safety Authority of Ireland, The Sea Fisheries Protection Authority, The Irish Shellfish Association and NUI Galway. The next ICMSS will be hosted in Mexico in May 2019 and further information on this will be published in due course.

Members of the local organising committee attending the official opening of the 11th ICMSS Conference

13th Session of the Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB)

This year marks the 25th anniversary of the Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB) established under the auspices of IOC of UNESCO. Over that period IPHAB has provided the international framework for regional and global coordination and prioritization of capacity development, research and strategic initiatives on HABs. The IPHAB met for its 13th session at UNESCO Headquarters, Paris, from

Participants in the 13th IPHAB session. IOC, Paris, 3-5 May 2017

3-5 May 2017. The Panel reviewed the many activities and results completed during 2015-2016 and noted the continued broad engagement of the science and management community in activities. The major achievements presented at IPHAB included:

- (i) the formal establishment of GlobalHAB, appointment of science steering committee members, and finalizing of the Science and Implementation Plan;
- (ii) development of an IOC-IAEA-FAO-WHO inter-agency strategy for research and monitoring on Ciguatera;
- (iii) implementation of sixteen training courses and training-through-research projects;
- (iv) continued development of the IPHAB-IODE Harmful Algae Information System including HAEDAT;
- (v) continued publication of the IOC Harmful Algae News;
- (vi) progress on the preparation of the first Global HAB Status Report;
- (vii) progress on the preparation of a Guidance Manual on HABs and Desalination;
- (viii) development of regional activities within ANCA, FANSA, HANA, WESTPAC-HAB and WESTPAC-TMO;
- (ix) the work of the ICES-IOC WGHABD and ICES-IOC-IMO WGBOSV; and
- (x) the continued vital partner-

ships with SCOR, ICES, PICES, IAEA and ISSHA. The Panel was also briefed on the IOC Capacity Development Strategy; the UN Sustainable Development Goals 14; and the OBIS database by IOC staff.

The IOC-coordinated HAB Programme is the only global intergovernmental effort to understand, manage and mitigate the harmful effects of algal blooms, and has therefore maintained a critical leadership role via IPHAB. Particularly noteworthy is the progress on inter-sessional IPHAB activities, including efforts by Task Teams to maintain an updated taxonomic list of HAB taxa and revisions to the nomenclature, identification and structures of novel phyco-toxins, and associated toxicological effects. Combined with IPHAB-sponsored initiatives on mapping biogeographical information on HAB events, these data-bases are essential to sustain both research and monitoring strategies.

The Panel has shown flexibility and adaptive capacity since its inception, modifying its functions and tasks to address emerging global priorities for ocean research and monitoring as defined by IOC. The IPHAB has aligned its priorities to address the four IOC overarching themes:

- i. Healthy Ocean Ecosystems;
- ii. Early Warning for Ocean Hazards;
- iii. Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation and
- iv. Enhanced Knowledge of Emerging Science.

Exciting new elements of HAB research have benefited immensely from the recognition by IPHAB of the importance of linkages to ocean observational systems and the effects of global change.

The Panel made decisions for priorities 2018-2019 for international HAB activities to be implemented by the IOC UNESCO and IPHAB partners. The Decisions concern the following:

- (i) IOC/HAB Training and Capacity Building Programme;
- (ii) Regional HAB Programme Development, continuation with revised Terms of Reference of the IPHAB;
- (iii) Task Team on the development of a Global HAB Status Report;
- (iv) Task Team on a Global Strategy on Ciguatera for Improved Research and Management; (v) Task Team on Harmful Algae and Desalination of Seawater;
- (vi) Task Team on Biotoxin Monitoring, Management and Regulations;
- (vii) Task Team on Algal Taxonomy, and
- (viii) Task Team on Harmful Algae and Fish Kills.

Dr. Gires Usup (Malaysia) was reelected as Chair and Dr. Allan Cembella (Germany) was reelected as Vice-Chair.

Contact: hab.ioc@unesco.org. More information and updates on activities at <http://hab.ioc-unesco.org>

Forthcoming events

11th International Conference on Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates

The University of Bordeaux (France) is the organiser of the 11th International Conference on Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates, DINO11, which will be held from 17-21 July 2017 at Bordeaux, France. This series of conference was first held in 1978 in Colorado Springs, Colorado (United States) (DINO1) and the 11th DINO meeting will be held for the first time in France.

Dinoflagellates and their cysts have shown major research interest for both, biologists working with modern dinoflagellates and geologists working with fossil dinoflagellates. From a biological viewpoint, this major plankton group has major interests in their taxonomy, genetics and ecology, and particularly in the study of toxic dinoflagellates (e.g. *Alexandrium*, *Dinophysis*) that can endanger human health through intoxication of shellfish or other organisms higher up the food chain. From a geological viewpoint, fossils dinoflagellate cysts are routinely used in biostratigraphy and palaeoclimatological applications. The international conference DINO11 will serve as a platform for exchanges between biologists and geologists concerning all these themes.

More information can be found on: <http://www.laplf.org/dino11/calque-dino11.htm>

Session on Ciguatera at the 10 IPFC (Grant applications still open!)

A theme session on ciguatera, *Ciguatera fish poisoning in the Indo-Pacific region: incidence, toxin dynamics, impacts on socio-ecosystems, and risk management*,

will be held at the **10 Indo-Pacific Fish Conference** (10 IPFC), 2-6 October 2017, Tahiti, French Polynesia (<https://ipfc10.criobe.pf/>).

Organizers: Mireille Chinain, Susanna Piovano, Jean Turquet, Marie-Yasmine Dechraoui-Bottein (mchinain@ilm.pf; susanna.piovano@usp.ac.fj; Turquet.arde@orange.fr; M-Y.Bottein@iaea.org)

The Ciguatera session (H5) is planned as part of Theme H (The Future of Fish and Human Interactions). The call for abstract is open: <https://ipfc10.criobe.pf/program/call-for-abstracts/>

Scope: Fish products are the nutritional basis of many island populations globally. Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) results from the consumption of fish that have accumulated ciguatoxins (CTXs) produced by benthic dinoflagellates in the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa*. Over the past decades, the frequency and distribution of CFP have increased significantly in the Indo-Pacific region, a likely consequence of numerous environmental changes in coastal and lagoon ecosystems. Despite increased knowledge about the impacts of climatic cycles and biogeography of *Gambierdiscus*, ciguatera events are still very difficult to predict. Likewise, the uptake,

tissue distribution, accumulation and toxicity of CTXs in fish are still poorly understood. The existence of numerous structural variants (congeners) of the toxin, and the lack of a duly validated reference test for CTXs both constitute a major obstacle in the sustainable exploitation of fish resources. In addition to the direct effects of ciguatera on public health and the economy of nations highly dependent on fish consumption, the fear of ciguatera often leads to reduced fishing in many indigenous Pacific populations, which reminds us that the impact of ciguatera risk must also be examined from sociological and societal perspectives and not only from a public health standpoint. Recently, several initiatives to implement a more efficient management of CFP risk globally have emerged within the scientific community. The main objective of this session is to present the recent advances in these research fields and to foster networking between scientists and stakeholders concerned with seafood safety.

Expected Audience: The targeted audience includes researchers (biologists, eco-toxicologist, modelists, economists, etc.) and managers interested in marine biotoxins and seafood safety issues. A group of 20 attendees from the Pacific region, Japan, Europe, and La Réunion is expected.

Student Grants Opportunities

Two grants could be of interest to HAN readers:

Grant 3: Ciguatera fish poisoning in the Indo-Pacific region: incidence, toxin dynamics, impacts on socio-ecosystems, and risk management

Grant 5: Women in Marine Sciences in the Indo-Pacific

Depending on the number and the quality of applicants, each grant could include one of the following three options: 1/ flight, accommodation and registration fees; 2/ accommodation and registration fees; or 3/ only registration fees.

Applications must be submitted before the 30th June 2017.

Photo from Institut Louis Malarde, French Polynesia, in Clausing et al, *IOC Manual and Guides* 59, 2016

6th International Symposium

“Marine and Freshwater Toxins Analysis”

22-25 October 2017, Baiona, Spain

Website: <http://biotoxinsmeeting.org/>

Topics:

- Advances in the analysis of existing and emerging marine and freshwater toxins.
- Mass spectrometry, molecular methods, toxicity assays, bioassays and screening tests.
- Structural characterization of new potential toxins.
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30 July 2017: Abstract submission
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Ted Smayda in Memoriam

10 April 2017

This year the HAB and research community lost another giant intellect. Professor Theodore J. Smayda, (Ted as he preferred to be called) passed away after a period of illness. A graduate of the Braarud School of phytoplankton ecology of Oslo, Norway, Ted held unique skills and insights into phytoplankton dynamics including those of HAB species. Author of over 150 peer reviewed publications and numerous book chapters, he remained a prolific writer and active researcher until the last days. His command of the literature in all languages was legendary and his ability to synthesize information from disparate sources was truly a skill few mastered with his proficiency. His inquisitive mind probed continually for major principles governing the dynamics of phytoplankton which were constantly used to stimulate his many students and colleagues alike. Always willing to listen, Ted developed ideas, questions and testable hypotheses with novice students to well established colleagues alike. Generous with his thoughts and ideas, he freely shared these through his many presentations at meetings, symposia and invited seminars. Among his many scientific accomplishments, Ted took pride in the excellent library holdings at the GSO Pell Library in which he personally scoured sources for pertinent literature. This was in keeping with an overriding philosophy of providing an environment where the mind was the limiting factor and all else was provided. Another scientific accomplishment he was particularly proud of was the long term Narragansett Bay Time Series, a data set beginning in 1959 and continuing weekly into the late 1990s. These data, obtained for various stations in Narragansett Bay but specifically for Station 2 that was sampled weekly over the entire period, remains one of the most complete phytoplankton data sets to date. Unlike other long-term data sets, this was one conducted on whole water samples, detailed species observations to a significant level and included physical chemi-

Ted Smayda at the Scientific Symposium on Harmful Algal Blooms and Climate Change in Gothenburg, Sweden May 19–22, 2015 (Photo Joe Silke)

cal data. The legacy of this data set will be available to all in the near future. The data set was also a cohesive element for his students who all contributed to its completion and often generated the hypotheses realized in their thesis research and subsequent publications. Analysis of these data resulted in Ted's understanding of the open niches provided for HAB species development, phytoplankton patterns occurring over unexpected periods spanning several years and trends significant to understanding effects of climate change. Ted's unique view of looking at HAB events as "Rosetta Stones", giving us insights into functioning of complex marine environments where we have few tools to dissect their elements arose from investigating this dataset. He continuously looked through a microscope, knew the species and was able to document their changes in time and

in various environments. This occurred at a time when skills at the taxonomic level were disappearing for more convenient but less informative and labor intensive methods. The foundation of these insights will provide stimulus for ideas for many years to come. In a personal vein, Ted was a happy family man, enormously proud of his children and their accomplishments and dearly loved nature including his beloved gardens and pond environment. His love for languages continued and was revealed in his private writing of poetry. A mentor, teacher, perpetual student and lover of knowledge, Ted will be sorely missed but deeply remembered through his enormous legacy of literature, ideas, and continued stimulus to know more. His contributions will continue for yet many years.

Carmelo R. Tomas

University of North Carolina Wilmington, USA

Some of Ted key publications

Smayda TJ 2008. Complexity in the eutrophication-harmful algal bloom relationship, with comment on the importance of grazing. *Harmful Algae* 8, 140-151

Smayda TJ & CS Reynolds 2002. Community assembly in marine phytoplankton: application of recent models to harmful dinoflagellate blooms. *J Plankton Res* 23: 447-461

Smayda TJ 2002. Turbulence, water-mass stratification and harmful algal blooms: An alternative view. *Harmful Algae* 1, 95-112

Smayda TJ 1997. Harmful algal blooms: their ecophysiology and general relevance to phytoplankton blooms in the sea. *Limnol Oceanog.* 42: 1137-1153

Smayda, TJ 1990 Novel and nuisance phytoplankton blooms in the sea: evidence for a global epidemic. In, E. Granéli, B. Sundström, L. Edler and D.M. Anderson (eds.) *Toxic Marine Phytoplankton*. Elsevier, New York, pp 29-40

The Effects of Climate Change on the World's Oceans

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

Deadline to submit material for HAN 58:
8th September 2017

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Lay-out

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